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Research Article

**A DETAILED REVIEW ON FORMULATION AND
CHARACTERIZATION OF AN IMMEDIATE RELEASE SOLID
ORAL DOSAGE FORM CONTAINING AN ESTROGEN
DERIVATIVE**Ashish D. Gadge¹, Dr Aijaz A. Shaikh², Dr.K. R. Biyani³^{1,2,3}Department of Pharmaceutics Anuradha college of Pharmacy Chikhali Dist-Buldana-443201**Abstract:**

The goal of the dissertation titled "Formulation and characterization of an immediate release solid oral dosage containing an estrogen derivative" was to create a stable and reliable dosage form. The test tablet closely resembled the size, shape, and color of the innovator's reference formulation. Moreover, the in vitro dissolution profile of the test formulation closely matched that of the innovator's reference formulation across all tested media.

A generic contraceptive tablet was developed to match the innovator's product. The developed product is safe, effective, and pharmaceutically equivalent to the reference product.

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INTRODUCTION:**Immediate Release Tablet:**

An immediate release (IR) medication form breaks down rapidly and dissolves completely to release the active ingredients. One of the most appealing ways to administer drug is probably orally. This is probably the most convenient way to administer medication-by mouth. The tablet is widely preferred as an oral dosage form due to its simplicity in manufacturing, ease of administration, precise dosing, greater stability compared to liquid forms, and resistance to tampering compared to capsules. The bioavailability of a drug depends on factors such as in vivo disintegration, solubility, and various physiological variables. Recently, scientists have focused on developing fast-disintegrating tablets, also known as instant-release tablets. This is achieved by using appropriate diluents and super disintegrants. The large surface area of the gastric mucosa promotes drug absorption, and the GI tract provides enough fluid to aid in the breakdown of the dosage form and the dissolution of the medication. For this reason, the oral route continues to be the recommended way of medicine delivery even with developments in innovative drug delivery technologies. Oral administration accounts for at least 90% of all medications used to generate a systemic impact. Recently, there has been a lot of research focused on tablets that dissolve quickly since both elderly and juvenile patients like them. Furthermore, the tablet's rapid disintegration improves in the drug's solubility.

The absorption of a drug is influenced by its solubility in gastrointestinal fluids and its ability to permeate across the gastrointestinal membrane, which ultimately affects its bioavailability. The solubility of a drug is largely determined by its physical and chemical properties. However, the speed at which a drug dissolves is significantly impacted by the disintegration of the tablet. Because the tablet's surface area is limited, it will disintegrate more slowly than a dissolving tablet. A batch of tablets must fulfill the required disintegration parameters in order to pass the official disintegration test. An essential component of tablet formulations, disintegrants are added to tablets to cause them to break when they come into contact with fluid. This process of separating necessary particles prior to drug dissolution is called the disintegration process, and the excipients that contribute to this process are called disintegrates.

Advantages of IR tablets:

- ▶ Increased convenience and improved compliance
- ▶ Improved stability
- ▶ Suitable for controlled release (CR)

activity/sustained release (SR) actives

- ▶ Permits excessive drug loading
- ▶ Capacity to offer liquid therapeutic properties in a solid form [3]

Disadvantages of IR tablets:

- ▶ For a longer period of time a single dosage of a conventional dosage form is not enough to maintain drug blood levels within the therapeutic range.
- ▶ Therapeutic "steady state" blood levels can be achieved with repeated administration of conventional dose forms at regular intervals, as long as the dosage amount and frequency of administration remain stable. But there are a lot of possible drawbacks to this strategy as well.
- ▶ Even after achieving the so-called "steady state" condition, the drug's blood level varies across subsequent dose intervals.
- ▶ A patient may be overmedicated or undermedicated for a while if their C_{max} and C_{min} values climb or fall outside of the drug's therapeutic range due to the unavoidable volatility of steady state blood levels.
- ▶ Therapy failure or inefficiency may result from noncompliance with dose regimens that need regular administration on the part of the patient.

Desired Criteria for IR Drug Delivery System:

- ▶ When taking a solid dose, it should rapidly dissolve or break down in the stomach. When it comes to liquid dose forms, taste masking should work well with them
- ▶ Be portable and worry-free about fragility
- ▶ Possess a pleasant mouthfeel
- ▶ It should not leave much or any residue in the mouth after oral administration.
- ▶ Show minimal vulnerability to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity.
- ▶ Be cheaply produced at low cost utilizing standard processing and packaging equipment.

Ethinyl Estradiol:

Ethinyl Estradiol (EE) is an Estradiol used as a contraceptive. Ethinyl Estradiol was granted Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval on 25 June 1943. EE is an estrogenic drug that is commonly used with progestin in birth control tablets [1]. EE was once generally used to treat a broad range of conditions including gynecological diseases, menopausal symptoms, and several hormone-sensitive cancers [2].

Typically, it is administered orally, it is also employed in patch and vaginal ring forms. Hans

Herloff Inhoffen and Walter Hohlweg created EE at Schering in 1938 with the intention of increasing estrogen's oral bioavailability. This was accomplished by adding an ethinyl group to estradiol's carbon. Mestranol was soon replaced by ethinyl estradiol in tablets and pills intended for contraception. EE is a versatile tool. It is frequently used in combination oral contraceptives (COC), also referred to as birth control, to prevent pregnancy through sexual activity. EE is a common ingredient in birth control formulations.

That not only prevents pregnancy but also improves acne, menstrual problems, and irregular menstruation [20].

Menopausal hormone treatment is another use for EE [21]. A synthetic estrogen called Ethyl Estradiol

that inhibits gonadotrophic hormone to delay ovulation and (LH) luteinizing hormone reduces endometrial vascularization [21].

While it is administered once daily, its effects last for an extended period. Additionally, because overdoses usually do not result in major side effects, its therapeutic index is broad. Counselling should be given to patients on their risk of thrombotic events. EE is a synthesized estrogenic substance. One of the body's many reactions to estrogen use is a reduction in bone density. Combination oral contraceptives, or COCs, block sperm from traveling by thickening cervical mucus, suppressing gonadotropin hormones, and preventing endometrial changes that are required for the implantation of a fertilized egg [21]. Moreover, it raises sex hormone binding globulin levels [23].

Material and Instruments/Equipment's:

Table No 1: List of material used in formulation

Sr.No.	Ingredient	Function
1.	Ethinyl Estradiol	Active
2.	Anhydrous Lactose monohydrate	Diluent
3.	Microcrystalline Cellulose	Diluent
4.	D&C Yellow #10	Colorant
5.	FD&C Yellow #6	Colorant
6.	Povidone	Binder
7.	DL-Alpha Tocopherol	Anti-oxidant
8.	Polacrillin Potassium	Disintegrant
9.	Magnesium Stearate	Lubricant

It has been decided to use the similar excipients as per reference standard for generic product development.

Justification for the use of Excipients:

As the product is intended for US market, the excipients complying with USP/NF specifications were used for developmental studies. Moreover, specific technical grades of functional excipients have been selected to suit the dosage form, formulation process, and desired characteristics and quality attributes.

Excipients Grade Selection:

Based on the results of the excipient compatibility study, excipient types that were identical to the reference drug product formulation were selected for the development of the generic product. Based on prior formulation expertise and understanding

of excipients that have been effectively utilized in the authorized products, the excipient grade selection and supplier were chosen. In further formulation development investigations, the amounts of excipients utilized in the formulation were examined.

Lactose Anhydrous:

Synonym Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance Super Tab 21 AN, super Tab 22AN, Super Tab 24AN
C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁
342.3 g/mol Filler/Diluent
white, or creamy white, hard crystalline material

Selection of Diluent (Lactose Anhydrous):

Lactose Anhydrous is mentioned in Reference product's leaflet. So, it was decided to use water soluble diluents as lactose, to achieve desired

dissolution. The Handbook of Excipients, edited by Rowe et al., sixth edition, indicates that lactose is utilized as a diluent in the preparation of standardized triturates of potent drugs, which aids in the subsequent mixing or blending processes during manufacturing operations. Based on required characteristics of tablets & referring to Reference product's leaflet, it was decided to use lactose anhydrous as a diluent. Manufacturer of Lactose is DFE Pharma which is a reliable and global vendor. Compendia status of Lactose is Ph. Eur./ USP-NF.

Microcrystalline Cellulose:

Synonym Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance Avicel PH-101, Microcel MC 102.

C₁₄H₂₆O₁₁

370.35 g/mol Diluent

white, odorless, tasteless, fibrous powder composed of porous particles

Selection of Diluent (Microcrystalline Cellulose):

Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) is a commonly utilized ingredient in oral tablet and capsule compositions. It is mostly utilized as a diluent and binder in both wet granulation and direct compression procedures. Its utility in tableting extends to its lubricating and disintegrating properties, alongside its roles as a diluent and binder. Based on required characteristics of tablets & referring to Reference product's leaflet, it was decided to use Microcrystalline Cellulose as a diluent. Manufacturer of Microcrystalline Cellulose is Itacel Farmoquimica Ltda which is a reliable and global vendor. Compendia status of Microcrystalline Cellulose is Ph. Eur./ USP-NF.

Povidone:

Synonym Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance Kollidone 25, Kollidone 30 Povidone K30

C₆H₉N O₁

364.95 g/mol Binder

Yellow-To-Brown Hygroscopic Powder

Selection of Binder (Povidone):

Povidone is mostly used in solid dosage forms; in the wet granulation processes used to make tablets, its solutions act as binders. Moreover, powder mixes that have been mixed dry with povidone are

granulated in place using water, alcohol, or hydroalcoholic solutions. Povidone is also utilized in a number of topical and oral suspensions and solutions as a stabilizing, suspending, or viscosity increasing agent. Povidone K 25 grade selected as a binder. Manufacturer of Povidone is BASF which is a reliable and global vendor. Compendia status of Povidone is Ph. Eur./ USP-NF.

• Magnesium Stearate:

Synonym: Magnesium octadecanoate, octadecanoic acid Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance C₃₆H₇₄O₄

591.2 g/mol Lubricant

Light white, having a faint odour of stearic acid

Selection of Lubricant (Magnesium Stearate):

Mg stearate is the most employed lubricant in tablet manufacturing, typically used at concentrations ranging from 0.25% to 5% w/w for its lubricating properties. So, concentration of magnesium stearate in the final formulation was selected within the normal recommended range. Manufacturer of Magnesium Stearate selected was Peter Greven Nederland C.V. which is reliable and global vendor. Compendia status of magnesium stearate is USP- NF/ Ph. Eur.

Polacrillin Potassium:

Synonym Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance Divinylbenzene, potassium methacrylate polymer C₁₄H₁₈KO₂

254.370 g/mol

Disintegrant

Cream Coloured, Odorless and tasteless, free-flowing powder.

Selection of Disintegrant (Polacrillin Potassium):

Polacrillin potassium is a type of resin utilized in oral solid dosage forms within pharmaceutical formulations, serving as a tablet disintegrant typically at concentrations ranging from 2% to 10% w/w. Manufacturer of Polacrillin Potassium selected was **Ion**

Exchange which is reliable and global vendor. Compendia status of Polacrillin Potassium is USP/ Ph. Eur.

• DL Alpha Tocopherol:

Synonym

Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance DL-ALPHA-TOCOPHEROL, alpha-tocopherol, Ephanyl

C₂₉H₅₀O₂

430.7 g/mol Anti-Oxidant
yellow-brown viscous liquid

Selection of Antioxidant (DI Alpha Tocopherol):

DI Alpha Tocopherol is primarily used as an antioxidant in tablet manufacturing at concentrations between 0.001 - 0.05% w/w. So, concentration of DI Alpha Tocopherol in the final formulation was selected within the normal recommended range. Manufacturer of DI Alpha Tocopherol selected was BASF which is reliable and global vendor. Compendia} status of DI Alpha Tocopherol is USP/ Pb. Eur.

- **D & C Yellow No. 10 AI:**
- **Synonym Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance**
- **C.I. Acid Yellow 3 and D&C Yellow No. 10 C1sH9 N Na20sS2**

NA

Colorant Yellow Powder

- **FD&C Yellow No. 6 AI**

Synonym

Molecular formula Molecular weight Functional category Appearance

ACID FOOD YELLOW 3, ACID FOOD YELLOWS

C t6H9 N409S2

465.394 g/mol Colorant

Sun Shine Yellow Powder

Preformulation Study:

Ensuring the production of a safe, stable, and clinically effective dosage form is the goal of Preformulation study. These studies evaluate the effects of drug components' and excipients' physical and chemical properties on dosage form formulation, manufacturing processes, and the final product's pharmacokinetic and biopharmaceutical qualities. It may eventually be confirmed by a thorough study of physicochemical characteristics that there are no major obstacles to the development of the formulation.

Active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) characterization:

Organoleptic evaluation:

These initial traits are fundamental for identifying any substance accurately. The following physical properties of the API were examined.

1. Colour

Compressibility index and Hausner's ratio: Carr's index= $\frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}$

Tapped density

Hausner's index= $\frac{\text{Tapped Density}}$

Bulk Density

2. Taste

3. Odor

Determination of solubility:

The drug's solubility was evaluated according to Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) guidelines. Solubility testing was conducted using five different buffers across a pH range from 1.2 to 10, and additional solubility studies were performed using various solvents.

Bulk density:

Apparent density is another name for bulk density. It is calculated by dividing a powder's bulk volume by mass. It mostly depends on elements including the size distribution, shape, and tendency of the particles to bind together.

The API was carefully weighed, then put through a #40 sieve and put into a graduated cylinder with a capacity of 100 millilitres. The apparent volume (VO) is the measurement of the volume that was made without any compression. The volume of a given quantity of powder sample that has been sifted into a graduated measuring cylinder is used to measure bulk density.

$$\text{Bulk Density} = M/VO \quad (1)$$

Where,

M=Mass of powder taken.

Vo= Apparent untapped volume.

Tapped Density:

Tapped density is a controlled density achieved by tapping a volumetric measuring cylinder filled with powder from a specified height using a mechanical device. The Electrolab USP apparatus was employed for measuring tapped density.

The API was accurately weighed, sieved through an #18 screen, and transferred into a 100 ml graduated cylinder. The cylinder was mechanically tapped to settle the powder under its own weight, achieving a consistent drop of 14 ± 2 mm at a rate of 300 drops per minute (Drops/Min). Subsequently, the cylinder was placed on the tapped density apparatus. Following 500 initial taps, the tapped volume (Y1) was recorded to the nearest graduated unit. After an additional 1250 taps, the tapped volume (V2) closest to the graduated units was noted. Tapped density was then calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Tapped Density} = M/V2 \quad (2)$$

$$\times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$(4)$$

Table No.2: Scale of flow ability

Sr. No.	Compressibility Index(%)	Flow character	Hausner's Ratio
1.	≤ 10	Excellent	1.00-1.11
2.	11-15	Good	1.12- 1.18
3.	16-20	Fair	1.19- 1.25
4.	21-25	Passable	1.26- 1.34
5.	26-31	Poor	1.35 - 1.45
6.	32-37	Very poor	1.46- 1.59
7.	> 38	Very, very poor	> 1.60

Angle of Repose:

The height cone method was used to calculate the granules' angle of repose. Granules were poured into a funnel that had been adjusted to the correct height. On a graph paper that was fastened to a horizontal surface, they were allowed to flow downward, and the angle of repose was computed using the formula.

$$\tan\theta = \frac{2h}{D} \quad (5)$$

Where, h = height and D = diameter of the pile respectively.

Table No.3: Flow Properties and Corresponding Angle of Repose

Sr. No	Flow property	Angle of repose
1.	Excellent	25-30
2.	Good	31-35
3.	Fair- aid not needed	36-40
4.	Passable - may hang-up	41-45
5.	Poor - must agitate,	46-55
6.	Very poor	56-65

Loss on Drying

The Loss on Drying (LOD) test is conducted to quantify the amount of water and volatile substances in a sample after drying it under controlled conditions. The moisture content in the API was assessed using a moisture analyzer, with the procedure outlined as follows: Approximately 2 grams of API was placed on a plate in a Sartorius moisture analyzer. The sample was heated at 105°C for 5 minutes, and the observed loss on drying was recorded.

$$\text{Lod} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Particle Size Determination

Particle size and shape area are two of the most significant characteristics affecting a drug's rate of dissolution as well as its potential bioavailability. Additionally, particle form and size have a significant impact on how homogenous powder mixes are in a blender. Because particle size determines the surface area that may be used for oxidation and hydrolysis, it can also have an impact on a medicinal substance's stability. Surface area has a significant impact on stability and is essential

for interacting with excipients in tablet dosage forms. Sieve analysis was used to assess the API's particle size. The Malvern mastersizer 3000 used laser diffraction to measure the API's particle size.

Drug Excipients Compatibility Study

Drugs excipient compatibility studies are essential for creating a final dosage form that is well-formulated and allows the drug to interact with one or more excipients as the process scales up from clinical trials to commercialization and ultimately to the patient. With a varied ratio for the drug and excipient according to this functionality, doing these tests early in the development process might potentially limit the risk of drug product stability and speed up drug development. The recommended quantity of each excipient was thoroughly combined with the weighed mixture of APL Blend was put into glass vials and sealed after being put through a sieve. These combinations were carefully packaged and stored in 5 mL glass vials with a white tint. In stability chambers, these vials are exposed to 25±2°C/60±5% RH (long term study), 30±2°C/65±5% RH (intermediate study), and 40±2°C/75±5% RH (accelerated study). Physical

changes such as caking, discoloration, liquefaction, etc. were detected in the samples.

Table No.4:Drug- Excipient Compatibility Study Composition Details

Sr.No.	Drug + Excipient mixture	Ratio
1.	Ethinyl Estradiol	1
2.	Ethinyl Estradiol + Anhydrous Lactose	1: 40
3.	Ethinyl Estradiol + Microcrystalline Cellulose	1: 10
4.	Ethinyl Estradiol + Povidone	1: 10
5.	Ethinyl Estradiol + Dl alpha tocopherol	1: 0.05
6.	Ethinyl Estradiol + Polacrillin Potassium	1: 10
7.	Ethinyl Estradiol + Magnesium Stearate	1: 0.5
8.	Ethinyl Estradiol + D&C Yellow No. 10 Al	1: 0.05
9.	Ethinyl Estradiol + FD&C Yellow No. 6 Al	1: 0.05
10.	Ethinyl Estradiol + AllExcipients	1: 40: 10: 10: 0.05: 10: 0.5: 0.05: 0.05

Strategy for Product Development:

Strategy was developed to find the best suitable formulation for the development of immediate release formulation for contraception.

Formulation strategy for development of immediate release by using Ethinyl Estradiol as derivative of Estrogen.

- ▶ The product design is aimed for developing formula for USA market.
- ▶ By using QbD approach optimization of formulation.
- ▶ Finalize the parameters with the help of optimal results
- ▶ Stability Study

Manufacturing Process Selection

To meet the bioequivalence criteria, we need to look for manufacturing process wherein relatively loose or porous granules are formed which result in faster rate of absorption from the test product and to meet our objectives following requirements were listed to arrive at the final target formulation.

- ▶ The proposed generic product should be immediate release with faster rate of absorption.
- ▶ Uniformity of mixing drug substance in the formulation, to be ensured by blend and content uniformity
- ▶ Formulation should provide acceptable physicochemical characteristics and bioequivalent with reference product.
- ▶ To arrive at robust and stable formulation.

These requirements were translated into a suitable system. This system can be described as high shear

mixer of wet granulation. Different methods are available like wet processes and dry processes for the preparation of immediate release tablets, but to achieve rapidly dissolving drug product with an intention to achieve faster rate of absorption (Tmax) comparable or slightly faster than reference product, high shear process was method of choice to proceed further for lab development. The process is simple and cost effective. This unit operation involves sifting, dry mixing, granulation, drying, sizing and compression steps. The reference product was thoroughly evaluated, based on experience and disintegration pattern of reference product and to arrive at cun-ent qualitative and quantitative formulation, several laboratory trials with changes in some qualitative and quantitative composition has been taken. Different trials were performed by adding binder and disintegrant in different concentration.

Stability Study (ICH Guideline)

The stability of the active ingredient is crucial in determining whether to accept or reject it during rational drug design or dosage form evaluation. Stability indicates that the physical properties of the drug have not significantly or unfavorably changed, and its chemical or biological activity has not declined from the manufacturing and packaging date to a level at or above the specified potency.

Stability testing evaluates how a drug's or product's properties change over time in different environmental situations including light, humidity, and temperature. This information aids in the establishment of suggested testing intervals, shelf-life standards, and storage conditions.

According to the "Stability Testing of New Drug

Substance and Products" (QIA) Guidelines published by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), stability tests are necessary before a drug may be registered in the US, Japan, or the European Union.

Stability Guidelines

$25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ $160 \pm 5\%$ RH (long term study)

$30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ $165 \pm 5\%$ RH (intermediate study)

$40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ / $75 \pm 5\%$ RH (accelerated study) in stability chamber for 3 months.

The selected formulation was packed in aluminum blister pack. They were then stored as per ICH guidelines for 1 months and evaluated for their, drug content and in vitro disintegration time and drug release.

Table No.05: Qualitative and Quantitative Composition

Sr. No.	Batch No.	F001		F002		F003	
	Ingredients	Qty (mg)/tab	% (w/w)	Qty (mg)/tab	% (w/w)	Qty (mg)/tab	% (w/w)
1	Anhydrous Lactose	67.47	84.33	68.27	85.33	60.27	75.33
2	Microcrystalline Cellulose	10.00	12.50	10.00	12.50	18.00	22.50
3	D&C Yellow #10Al 15%-20%	0.43	0.538	0.43	0.538	0.43	0.538
4	FD&C Yellow #6 Sunsetyel. FCF Al	0.07	0.088	0.07	0.088	0.07	0.088
5	Ethinyl Estradiol Micronized	0.01	0.013	0.01	0.013	0.01	0.013
6	Povidone	0.80	1.000	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.000
7	DLAlpha Tocopherol	0.02	0.025	0.02	0.025	0.02	0.025
8	Isopropyl Alcohol	q.s.	--	q.s.	--	q.s.	--
9	Polacrillin Potassium	0.40	0.500	0.40	0.500	0.40	0.500
10	Magnesium Stearate	0.80	1.000	0.80	1.000	0.80	1.000
Tablet Weight		80.00	100.0	80.00	100.0	80.00	100.0

Manufacturing Procedure:**► Shifting:**

- 1) Sift Lactose Anhydrous through #80 sieve and collect screened and retained fraction separately in polybag.
- 2) Sift Microcrystalline Cellulose through #40 sieve and collect in polybag.
- 3) Co-sift D&C Yellow #10, FD&C Yellow #6 along with screened Lactose Anhydrous twice through #80 sieve and collect in polybag. Label it as color premix.

► Binder Solution Preparation:

- 4) Take 60 gm of Isopropyl Alcohol in S.S. container. To it add DL Alpha Tocopherol and stir for 5 minutes.
- 5) Add Povidone to the solution of step 4 and stir until it is completely dissolved.
- 6) Add Ethinyl Estradiol API to the solution of step 5 and stir until clear solution is formed. Label it as API-Binder solution.

► Dry Mixing and Granulation:

- 7) Load the material of step 1, step 2 and step 3 into RMG SL capacity and dry mix the material for 10 minutes with following parameters.

Table No 6: Dry Mixing Parameters

Stage	Time	Impeller Speed	Chopper Speed
Dry Mixing	10 minutes	100 rpm	Off

- 8) Granulate the material of step 7 with API-Binder solution of step 6 with following parameters as mentioned below.

Table 7. : Granulation Parameters

Stage	Time	Impeller Speed	Chopper Speed
Binder Addition	120 seconds	100 rpm	Off
Rinsing (20gm)	60 seconds	100 rpm	Off
Kneading	60 seconds	100 rpm	Off

► Drying and Sizing:

- 9) Discharge the wet mass and dry until LOD of NMT 2.0% w/w is achieved.
- 10) Sift the dried granules through #40 sieve and collect in polybag.

► Pre-Lubrication:

- 11) Sift Polacrillin Potassium through #40 sieve and collect in polybag.
- 12) Load the material of step 10 and step 11 into a blender SL capacity and mix for 10 minutes at 12 rpm.

► Lubrication:

- 13) Sift magnesium stearate through #60 sieve and mix it with material of step 12 for 4 minutes at 12 rpm.

► Compression:

- 14) Compress the lubricated blend using 5.5 mm, round, standard concave B tooling punches.

Table 8: Physicochemical Parameters of Lubricated Blend and Compressed Tablets

Batch no+ Parameters	F001	FOO2	F003
LOD of Lub. Blend% w/w	1.26	1.51	2.08
Average weight of the tablets (mg)	80.6	80.8	80.4
Thickness (mm)	3.02-3.06	3.02-3.05	2.98-3.03
Hardness (N)	36-47	36-45	36-45
Friability (%)	0.15	0.15	0.19
Disintegration Time	05M-10S	02M-30S	02M-24S
Assay(% w/w)	100.00	99.80	97.00

Summary And Conclusion

Summary

The goal of the dissertation titled "Formulation and characterization of an immediate release solid oral dosage containing an estrogen derivative" was to create a stable and reliable dosage form. The test tablet closely resembled the size, shape, and color of the innovator's reference formulation. Moreover, the in vitro dissolution profile of the test formulation closely matched that of the innovator's reference formulation across all tested media.

A generic contraceptive tablet was developed to match the innovator's product. The developed product is safe, effective, and pharmaceutically equivalent to the reference product.

CONCLUSION:

- ▶ Generic Ethinyl Estradiol Tablet USP 0.01 mg was developed using API from industrial Chimica S.R.L.
- ▶ The formulation composition was determined through Formulation Development Studies #1 to #4 using the Quality by Design (QbD) approach.
- ▶ The quantities of binder and disintegrant were established during Study #2.
- ▶ During Study #3, the amount of magnesium stearate was determined and finalized for the formulation to prevent tablet picking and sticking.
- ▶ The size, shape and colour of the tablet were almost identical and comparable with the innovators reference formulation.
- ▶ Addition, the in vivo dissolution profile of the formulation matches that of the innovator's reference across all tested media.
- ▶ The developed product was safe, efficacious, cost effective and pharmaceutical equivalence to the reference product.

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